

Non-transitivity in Theoretical and Practical Contexts: Flaw or Function

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Abstract

This paper is a report of an invited session organized at JSM2024 under the title above. We define two broad subclasses of non-transitivity: first as a realization of random variables and second as a long-run property of random variables, we discuss examples of non-transitivity and ways to resolve this paradoxical behaviour of random variables.

Key Words: non-transitivity, intransitivity, win probability, win ratio

1. Introduction

The non-transitivity phenomenon is often illustrated through a classical example of a set of four "Efron dice". Scores on these dice are distributed in such a way that in the long run die A beats die B, B beats C, C beats D and D paradoxically beats A. Non-transitivity has been observed in machine learning/data science, econometrics, sports (tennis and chess), and recently in life sciences applications, for example in biology (Liao, et al. Survival of the weakest in non-transitive asymmetric interactions among strains of *E. coli*; Nature Comm (2020)) and clinical trials. Despite its presence across diverse fields, our understanding of its implications for analytical conclusions remains limited. The field is already divided on the acceptability of non-transitivity. Some proponents advocate for statistical methods that are exclusively transitive, such as comparisons of means. Conversely, others believe that when the time to all-cause death in a randomized trial forms a non-transitive loop, it provides crucial information, signifying the complexity in comparing the treatments under consideration. In this invited session, we have defined two classes of non-transitivity and ways to resolve non-transitivity of commonly used statistics.

The structure of this paper is as follows. Olga Demler notes that non-transitivity of the win ratio can be observed not only as a specific realizations of event types and times presented by Dr. David Oakes, but as a long-run behavior of random variables. In her presentation she focuses on situations where non-transitivity is a problem and when it can be ruled out. Arne Bathke discusses novel modifications to nonparametric testing procedures that can guarantee transitivity. David Oakes discusses the first type of non-transitivity as a realization of random variables that form a non-transitive loop. Dr. Oakes focuses on the win ratio, a novel important statistics that has already been used as a primary efficacy metric in several large randomized clinical trials. As a discussant, Thomas Lumley has put these three talks into the context of a general result that only statistics based on a univariate summary are transitive in all generality (Lumley, Gillen, 2016).

2. Summary of the Presentations

2.1 Non-transitivity of the Win Ratio and the AUC: a case for evaluating strength of stochastic comparisons (Olga Demler)

2.1.1 Motivation

Non-transitivity as long-run behavior was first studied by Steinhaus and Trybuła (Steinhaus H 1959) as a property of three or more random variables. They focus on the probability that one variable is stochastically greater than another in the long run (i.e. $\Pr(X>Y)>1/2$). Three random variables X , Y , and Z can form such an order that a non-transitive loop is constituted without a winner: $\Pr(X>Y)$ and $\Pr(Y>Z)$ and $\Pr(Z>X)$. They noted that this property pertains to random variables in general and studied conditions when this property may be present. This phenomenon was later popularized by (Gardner 1970) who noted an example of non-transitive dice developed by Efron as an illustration of this paradoxical property. Motivation of the present talk was an observation that a win proportion, win ratio and win odds (Finkelstein and Schoenfeld 1999; Pocock et al. 2012), novel statistics that have already been used to report results in several randomized controlled trials can also form a non-transitive loop. In this talk we studied this property in more detail.

We would like to point out two forms of violation of transitivity: one as a long-run behavior of random variables such as in Efron's dice (Gardner 1970) and the second one as a behavior of the *realizations* of random times to events coupled with specific events hierarchy. The latter is defined by David Oakes (Oakes 2025). We focus here on the former and call it "non-transitivity" as opposed to the other definition which we will call "intransitivity" to be consistent with the definition used by David Oakes.

Definitions.

Variables X , Y , and Z form a non-transitive loop if $\Pr(X>Y)$ and $\Pr(Y>Z)$ and $\Pr(Z>X)$. In clinical trials literature if X , Y and Z are times to event (also called the outcome, or the 0/1 endpoint of the trial) in a tree-arms trial, then $\Pr(X>Y)$ is also called win proportion. To translate the non-transitivity property into the context of clinical trials, we will assume an idealized situation where X , Y , and Z all take distinct values, and there is no censoring. The win ratio is a monotonic function of the win proportion, therefore whenever the win proportion forms a non-transitive loop, the win ratio also forms a non-transitive loop. Under these assumptions, both quantities are equivalent and therefore win odds can also form non-transitive loops.

2.1.2 Main Results

Existence

First, we would like to illustrate the existence of continuous variables that can form non-transitive loop. In Figure 1 we present the theoretical example of three random variables that form a non-transitive loop with win proportions of .52.

Figure 1. Example of three random variables x , y and z that form non-transitive loop with win proportion of .52.

In a manuscript currently under peer view (Demler and Demler 2023) we present an example of a large randomized controlled trial in which time to all-cause death in four arms forms a non-transitive loop. It means that if we ask a question in which arm participants live longer than participants in

other arms, we cannot identify a winning treatment. Indeed, if A, B, C, and D are time to all-cause death in the four arms of this trial, then $\Pr(A>B)$ and $\Pr(B>C)$ and $\Pr(C>D)$ and $\Pr(D>A)$.

Decision about treatment efficacy is a high-stakes decision not because clinical trials are expensive but because patients, when making a decision to follow their clinician’s recommendation, to take a medication, trust that treatment efficacy is evaluated from all possible aspects. When treatments form a non-transitive loop with respect to such an important metric as time to all-cause mortality, it is a sign that there is no clear winner. This fact should be reported and perhaps it is unethical not to report it.

The question is then, when we can rule out non-transitivity when reporting win proportions and win ratios?

Lumley and Gillen(Lumley and Gillen 2016) showed that transitivity can be guaranteed only for univariable statistics (comparisons of means and other univariate statistics). Head-to-head comparisons such as win proportions, and other win statistics can be non-transitive. In this talk, we discuss conditions on distribution functions of times to event that can rule out non-transitivity of head-to-head comparisons illustrating this property with win statistics.

Sufficient conditions of transitivity of three independent random variables are:

- Three Binomial random variables are always transitive.
- Three Normally distributed random variables are always transitive.
- Three Log-normally distributed random variables are always transitive
- Random variables with the same pdfs up to a shift are transitive(Trybuła 1961).
- Three random variables with symmetric pdfs are always transitive(Lebedev 2019).

Do these conditions rule out non-transitivity of win statistics for all practical purposes? To answer this question, we present histograms of onset dates for different diagnoses reported in the UK Biobank (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of dates of onset of several diagnoses reported in the UK Biobank.

From Figure 2 we conclude that these examples of the distributions of dates of events are non-symmetric and vary from diagnosis to diagnosis. It is not clear how intervention therapy affects distribution of dates of events and this could be investigated in future studies. Another important direction is how censoring affects transitivity of win ratio and other win statistics. Accommodation of censoring in win ratio and other win statistics was studied by several authors(Dong, Mao, et al. 2020; Dong, Huang, et al. 2020) and it is important to integrate it in the context of their transitivity/non-transitivity. Another question that needs to be answered is how design affects statistics that can violate transitivity assumption. Should we use inverse probability weighting to match distribution to a target subpopulation of interest?

2.1.3 Non-transitivity: flaw or function?

The field is divided about how to treat non-transitivity. Poddiakov wrote a comprehensive review on the role of non-transitivity across the fields of science(Poddiakov 2024). He notes that “The

belief in transitivity of objectively intransitive options and making transitive choices of such options are a fallacy.” I concur and argue that it is important to understand implications of non-transitivity when reporting results of randomized clinical trials. I also argue that statistics that can be non-transitive measure the strength of stochastic relationships between two random variables and as therefore it is important to develop new statistics that measure strength of stochastic relationships. On the other hand, Lumley and Gillen note that non-transitivity is probably rare in real data, recommend to focus on transitive statistics but acknowledge that the lack of transitivity represents a theoretical issue with real-world implications, particularly in regulated industries where consistent outcome preferences are essential.

Non-transitivity has an important function in bacterial ecology. Notably, non-transitivity is a driver of biodiversity. Liao et al (Liao et al. 2020) and others (Lehtinen et al. 2022) showed that non-transitivity ensures that it is not always the most toxic bacteria that win. Three strains of bacteria can form a non-transitive loop which ensures their existence in balance without one strain dominating all others. Non-transitivity is often observed in sports (Sanjaya, Wang, and Yang 2022). In econometrics non-transitivity was studied in relation to preference choice (Debreu 1954; Alós-Ferrer, Fehr, and Garagnani 2022; Arrow 1950) and voting (Arrow 1950) and its study continues to this day (Alós-Ferrer, Fehr, and Garagnani 2022). Brunner, Bathke, and others (Beck and Bathke 2024; Brunner, Bathke, and Konietschke 2018; Akritas, Arnold, and Brunner 1997) suggest ways to overcome non-transitivity by introducing casino approaches to head-to-head comparisons. Colleagues including Gowers in their Polymath project study how common is non-transitivity (Polymath 2022; Gowers T.). Given these results, we argue that non-transitivity is not a flaw but a function and as such should be studied. We recommend addressing non-transitivity directly, rather than relying on univariate statistics that overlook this property. By including in efficacy assessments statistics that can be non-transitive, we can be sure that treatments’ efficacy is broadly robust and avoid the situation when treatment is effective merely due to artificially limiting their efficacy assessment to transitive tests.

2.2 Non-transitivity in Nonparametric Comparisons (Arne Bathke)

2.2.1 Motivation

Non-transitivity may occur when applying well-established statistical inference procedures for the comparison of different treatments or subpopulations. There have been solutions proposed to avoid non-transitive decisions, and we will briefly review them. On the other hand, the occurrence of non-transitivity in any real data analysis may actually suggest that one should look at the data more closely, for example using an additional statistical functional that may shed light on the reasons for such non-transitivity. Seemingly paradoxical results in a data analysis may actually hint at interesting patterns deserving special attention.

2.2.2 Main Results

The most well-known nonparametric statistical procedures are based on a functional that is often referred to as the nonparametric relative effect (also known as, e.g., probabilistic index, win probability, or stochastic superiority). For two random variables X and Y , the pairwise nonparametric relative effect can be formulated as $\theta = P(X < Y) + \frac{1}{2} P(X = Y)$. For simplicity, we will usually omit the term $\frac{1}{2} P(X = Y)$ in the sequel, as it is not centrally relevant to the story being told here, although it is part of the precise definition of θ and certainly will matter when you have discrete data with ties.

Large values of θ indicate a tendency of Y to take larger values than X . If X and Y follow the same distribution, then $\theta = 1/2$, but the converse is not true: the relative effect θ also takes the value $\frac{1}{2}$ if X and Y come from, for example, two symmetric distributions with the same mean, but different variances.

Based on independent X - and Y -samples, unbiased and consistent estimation of the pairwise nonparametric relative effect θ is possible using the ranks of the X - and Y -values. This empirical version also forms the basis for the well-known rank sum test that is named after Wilcoxon, Mann,

and Whitney. Presumably, this is one of the main reasons why nonparametric statistics has often been considered synonymous with rank-based methods.

For comparisons involving more than two groups, the above-mentioned situation of Efron's paradoxical dice may occur, and thus comparisons using the pairwise nonparametric relative effects may yield the seemingly paradoxical result of

$$P(X_1 < X_2) < 1/2, P(X_2 < X_3) < 1/2, P(X_3 < X_4) < 1/2, \text{ and } P(X_4 < X_1) < 1/2.$$

It could even happen that each of the corresponding uses of the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney rank sum test turns out to be significant. Translating this into treatment effects with the same labeling, this could mean that treatment 1 is significantly better than 2, 2 better than 3, 3 better than 4, but 4 better than 1.

How can one avoid such a situation? The easiest, but perhaps least satisfying solution is to impose model classes in which the paradox simply cannot occur. For example, to assume pure location shift models in which all random variables originate from distributions with the same shape, but possibly different centers of location. Or to restrict oneself to considering only distribution functions which are ordered in the strict sense. A much more elegant solution however is to allow arbitrary distribution functions, but to base the overall assessment of the different groups not on pairwise comparisons, but on a test statistic that is constructed using comparisons of each group to a common reference group, that is, using quantities $\theta_i = P(Z < X_i)$, where the index i denotes the group, and Z is a random variable that follows the reference distribution.

For example, the reference distribution can be chosen as the sample size weighted average of all distribution functions involved. More precisely, if $X_{ij} \sim F_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, a$ (groups), $j = 1, \dots, n_i$, and all X_{ij} are independent, then the reference distribution can be chosen as the weighted average $H = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^a n_i F_i$ where N is the sum of all sample sizes n_i . This construction leads to the classic Kruskal-Wallis test in a natural way, and again the θ_i can be estimated in an unbiased and consistent manner using the ranks of the original observations. The weighting that is done through the sample sizes n_i is however rather arbitrary, and other weights may indeed be more advantageous, as we will elaborate below.

A completely different approach to dealing with non-transitivity in multi-group comparisons uses the pairwise comparisons (no reference group) and takes advantage of the observation that non-transitivity can only occur with nonsymmetric overlap of distributions. This suggests that explicitly investigating the overlap between the involved distributions will shed light on the underlying reasons when such seemingly paradoxical decisions happen.

2.2.3 Future Directions

In the previous subsection, we have mentioned two different research directions, and both necessitate further investigation.

First of all, the choice of the reference distribution warrants attention. Just because the use of the sample size weighted average distribution function is the most popular reference does not mean that it is necessarily the best choice. Indeed, it may even lead to further paradoxes, due to the fact that weighting by sample size has the effect that the inferential results may change depending on sample size assignments. In other words, for the exact same underlying distributions F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 , one may obtain opposing descriptive and inferential results, depending on the sample size allocation to the three treatment groups. Thus, the Kruskal-Wallis test (which uses the sample size weighted average distribution function as the reference distribution) may yield contradictory results for different allocation configurations - even when the underlying population distributions remain unchanged. This dependence on the relative sample size assignments can be removed easily by employing a different reference distribution. In most situations, a suitable reference distribution is simply the unweighted average of all involved distributions. Using the unweighted average then leads to test statistics based on pseudo-ranks instead of ranks (see also Brunner et al. 2018, Brunner et al. 2020, Zimmermann et al. 2021).

The second research direction follows the paradigm that non-transitivity in pairwise comparisons, if it occurs, carries meaning and information, and thus deserves to be examined further. To this end, a second statistical functional is needed. Just as the mean does not always suffice in describing a data set and needs to be complemented by the standard deviation, or the median by the interquartile range, there are many situations where the relative effect should be accompanied by an appropriate and complementing measure of dispersion such as the nonsymmetric niche overlap which quantifies how much of one distribution is “contained” in another one (Parkinson et al. 2018, Parkinson & Bathke 2019, 2022).

2.3 Potential intransitivity of the win ratio: Does it Matter and What do we Do About It? (David Oakes)

2.3.1 Motivation

Pocock et al. (2012), following Finkelstein and Schoenfeld (1999) popularized the win ratio for analysis of controlled clinical trials with multiple types of outcome event. The approach uses pairwise comparisons between patients in the treatment and control groups using a primary outcome, say time to death, with indeterminacies resolved where possible using a secondary outcome, say time to hospitalization. Preferences assigned by this method may not be transitive. Intransitivity occurs when potential follow-up time varies between patients and rankings based on primary events differ from those based on secondary events. In Oakes (2025) we derive some general properties of win-ratio preferences and provide numerical illustrations under simple models.

There are differences in terminology and concepts between this presentation and those discussed in subsequent sections of this submission. I reserve the term win-ratio to the case of two or more prioritized ranked outcomes with the possibility of indeterminacies of rankings in higher order outcomes being resolved by recourse to the lower order outcomes. The term win ratio can be used in relation to a single outcome, and may give rise to intransitivities of a different sort to those discussed here. To illustrate the point, any single roll of the four “Efron dice” discussed in the Introduction must necessarily provide a transitive sequence. Intransitivity arises when we consider the preferences when the dice are rolled repeatedly. Intransitivities that arise when probability distributions are applied over probability spaces on transitive outcome sets are a fascinating topic, as illustrated later in this report.

2.3.2 Main Results

In the win-ratio setting, unless all follow-up times are equal, see Oakes (2016), intransitivities are certain to occur in sufficiently large samples, but their overall frequency is low and there is no simple remediation of the problem. Any cyclic loop must contain a cyclic triplet, and of the three preferences in the triplet exactly one is determined by the primary outcome. Intransitivity is largely determined by reversals – pairs of individuals where preferences on primary and secondary outcomes are in opposite directions. If the $9! = 362880$ permutations of the nine event times (primary, secondary and censoring times) associated with three individuals are equally likely then the probability of a cyclic loop is $1/288 = 0.0035$, whereas that of a fully transitive set is 0.4410. These results, and others, are derived in Oakes (2025).

3. Discussion

3.1 Non-transitivity: threat or menace? (Thomas Lumley)

As Olga Demler argues in the first section of this paper, non-transitivity is a natural property of binary relations. In some settings it is desirable, such as the rock-paper-scissors game where it allows fair choices without needing a trusted source of random numbers. In other settings it is neither good or bad, but merely part of the way nature works. Demler mentions a non-transitive fitness relationship in bacteria, and one in lizards is described by Zamudio and Sinervo(2000). In yet other settings it is unavoidable: non-transitivity of pairwise voting preferences was noted by

Condorcet in the 18th century, and the point was hammered home by Arrow's Impossibility Theorem in the 20th century.

However, in statistical testing and decision theory I would argue that it is (a) undesirable and (b) typically comes from avoiding thinking carefully about the outcomes and the benefits and harms of different decisions.

When the whole purpose of a test or decision is to say which group is 'better' and which is 'worse', it is important that the decisions are in fact consistent with some definition of 'better' and 'worse'. That is, the decision should be consistent with some partial order on distributions. Ideally, it would be a total preorder, so any two distributions could either be ordered or declared equivalent (eg, distributions with the same mean under the t-test). If a total preorder is not possible, a partial order at least allows internal consistency in decision-making (eg, the rule of comparing survival curves with a logrank test only when they do not cross).

I think the most common source of non-transitivity is a reluctance to assign more than an ordering to observations with unattractive distributions. As an ordering on observations is not enough to determine an ordering on distributions, the consequence is either a fairly sparse partial order or a non-transitive relation. Assigning numbers is the only way around this problem in general, as Debreu's theorem reminds us: under mild assumptions, any linear preorder can be represented by a subset of the reals

4. Conclusions

Olga Demler:

Non-transitivity as a long-run behavior of random variables is a natural phenomenon that is reported in diverse fields of science. Its role in clinical research is not studied well. In this session we showed that win statistics (win proportion and win ratio) can form a non-transitive loop. We also demonstrate that we can guarantee transitivity of win statistics if certain assumptions are satisfied. We put forward a hypothesis that although head-to-head comparisons can be non-transitive, this is not a flaw but a function. Such statistics measure strength of stochastic relationship of random variables and as such provide additional information about their behavior that cannot be captured by univariate statistics that are always transitive. We propose to confront non-transitivity directly, study conditions when we can guarantee transitivity.

Arne Bathke:

Non-transitivity in nonparametric inference can indeed be circumvented by using a common reference distribution instead of relying on several pairwise comparisons. Then, the choice of the reference distribution matters. It would often be advantageous to use the unweighted average of the distribution functions instead of the popular sample size weighted average, as the results based on the latter can depend on sample size allocations. However, when performing pairwise comparisons, investigating possible sources of non-transitivity is highly recommended, and to this end, nonsymmetric measures of niche overlap can be very informative.

David Oakes:

As any sports enthusiast is aware, tie-breaking procedures often lead to potential intransitivities in preferences that can complicate rankings. The phenomenon extends to the analysis of win-ratio preferences when rankings of secondary events are used to resolve indeterminacies in rankings of primary events. It is essentially independent of the probability structure associated with the preferences. In most cases cyclic loops are rare and unlikely to be of serious practical concern but their existence does raise conceptual issues about the interpretation of the analysis.

5. Acknowledgements

OD is grateful for the support of her work by the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH, Zurich, Switzerland), and the following grants from the NHLBI at the NIH: R21HL167173,

K01HL135342 and 17IGMV33860009 from the American Heart Association. OD also reports no conflict of interests related to this study.

AB gratefully acknowledges the support of the WISS 2025 project 'IDA-Lab Salzburg' (20204-WISS/225/197-2019 and 20102-F1901166-KZP), as well as funding through the EXDIGIT (Excellence in Digital Sciences and Interdisciplinary Technologies) project, funded by Land Salzburg under grant number 20204-WISS/263/6-6022.

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